

Obstructions of Micro Women Entrepreneurs (A study in Guntakal Municipality, Anantapur Dist. A.P)

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ABSTRACT

This paper made an attempt to throw a light on impediments faced by micro women entrepreneurs in Guntakal Municipality of Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh (India). This study is based on primary data in which information is collected through questionnaires. The findings revealed that difficulty in finding funding to set up a business, inadequate family cum society support, unfriendly business environment, lack of marketing skills, difficulty in balancing homely affairs were some problems faced by women entrepreneurs. This study report highlights the fundamental problems that females are experiencing while setting up and growing their business.

Keywords: Micro Women Entrepreneurs, Impediments.

INTRODUCTION

According to the sixth economic census by Indian Ministry Of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Women entrepreneurs constitute only 8.05 million out of 58.5 million women entrepreneurs in India and just 10.56% of female entrepreneurship is being surveyed in Andhra Pradesh. Women entrepreneurs are those who think of a business enterprise, initiate it, undertake risks and handle economic uncertainty and operate the enterprise. Even though the traditional setup is changing, women have to go a long way to reach equal rights and positions.

Micro businesses are the family businesses employing one or two people whose main aim is to help themselves and their families earning a livelihood through it. Women startups face a series of problems right from the start till the firm functions.

OBJECTIVES

- To examine the complication and threats faced by female entrepreneurs.
- To understand the challenges faced by micro women entrepreneurs.
- To identify the potential way to overcome the problems of women entrepreneurs in their business.
- To effectively improve the changes in business practices.
- To provide suggestions for the growth of women entrepreneurs in the sample location taken for this work.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jyothi Rani and Sanjay Kumar Sinha (2016). This paper explains the entrepreneurial problems of women and changing entrepreneurial environment women are exposed to in rural India.

Swarnalatha K and Anuradha R.K (2014). This paper found that women in India face many problems and constraints to get ahead in their life in business. They should explore the prospects of starting a new enterprise, under take risks, introduce coordinate administration and control business and provide effective leadership in all aspects of business.

G.H. Barhate and Madhavi S Patgaonkar (2012). It is observed that women start business for several reasons like financial Support earning livelihood for family, independence etc. The size of the business owned by women in the informal sector is usually small and operated from their own residence successfully but women do not receive enough support from their family and from the government as well.

Sherly Thomas and LV Lavanya. This paper found that many women entrepreneurs by their own interest (or) in order to earn a living and support their family have come forward to take up challenges opportunities like entrepreneurship. Despite the problems and a host of other

problems that women entrepreneurs face in their journey on this path, they still dare to take up this challenging job in the present era.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a descriptive research work which is collected by the researcher. It is based on secondary data gathered from books, journals, magazines, and web papers. Primary data: A survey is being conducted with research instruments like personal interview schedules and questionnaires which comprises closed-ended and open-ended questions to 80 members from micro women entrepreneurs in a semi urban region like Anantapur district of Andhra Pradesh.

CHALLENGES FACED BY WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS LEADING MEN

The most significant obstacle for women entrepreneurs in Indian business era is the intense male dominated society (community) hierarchy that appoints man to a life of triumph (success) outside of the household and women are low profile appearances with him. This can lead to lack of dedication, lack of creativity and lack of adequate experience towards work. Financial Hurdles

Women entrepreneurs always suffer from “finding funding” the biggest hurdles faced by them entrepreneurs try to question the business persons “how would manage”, “how best is your idea”. Even applying for a loan under CGTMSE which is not collateral where the government takes guarantee, still it doesn’t work out. Socio Culture Problems

Most women entrepreneurs experience socio-cultural problems which hurts their ambition. The overwhelming impact of socio culture mind block around the family, society often makes a conscious choice not to scale up their aspiration, progression. Safety and Security. Safety and security is yet another hurdle women are facing now-a-days. The increases of community misdeeds and necessary for safety pushes everything down the priority list where there is a pressure to go through behind getting work. Family Ties

Even through the world stepping towards modernization, the Indian women entrepreneurs have to fight against deep rooted traditions and values within their family. These demands from family can stress the soul of a woman who is aiming to start up her own business.

FINDINGS

- 50% finding of this study revealed that women entrepreneurs are facing problems while doing business.
- 62.5 % of business women started their business with self-funding at the same time 35% procure loans from banks and 2.5% from credits.
- 50% of self-support, 32.5% from relatives, friends and some agencies as well as 17.5% assistance from their spouses.
- 77% of female entrepreneurs cope with illiteracy, lack of understanding, negative feedback, plus 22.5% deal with clumsy nature of customers.
- 65% negotiation, 20% storage facility moreover 15% price discrimination troubles a women entrepreneur while trading.
- 25% of communication and 5% of cost, quality risk is being surveyed at the time of procurement of goods.
- 20% of business women are not satisfied with their working hours (conditions).
- 17.5% witnessed that women entrepreneurs are not able to balance their work life.
- 12.5% loss is observed during business by female entrepreneurs.

SUGGESTION TO OVERCOME HURDLES OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR

- Accommodating with funding, contribution from family, relatives and society, generating support networks along with acknowledging successful stories of female entrepreneurs can help them to overcome several problems.
- Women in business need to be offered with loan schemes, subsidies and other financial funding to encourage them to indulge in business activities. The financial organization should provide sufficient capital to assist them.

- Members of family, friends, and relatives have to contribute towards upliftment of women entrepreneurs and encourage them to chase their dreams with right motivation to excel in every field.
- To overcome demanding, dissatisfaction or difficult customers one needs to find techniques like resolving their problems, offering possible solutions, attempt to come to an harmony will help the business women to deal with customers.
- Demonstrating unique value of product, introducing certain guarantees, return policies might provide answers to the questions while trading.
- Right information about getting quality materials, attractive packaging of products with cut price many more can minimize the obstacles of women entrepreneurs regarding procurement of goods.
- Equal contribution of work from family as well as assistance from subordinates or employees at work might help them to satisfy with their working conditions.
- Women are considered to possess strong leadership qualities, they certainly need to balance their work life.

CONCLUSION

At present women occupy nearly 48.04% of the total Indian population. It is recorded that the average growth rate of women enterprises are significantly lowered when compared to average growth rate of start-ups by men. To sufficiently create employment and economics on a local and national level, essential steps are needed to be opted like arranging entrepreneurial awareness, orientation and skill developed programs to women. Women entrepreneurs at micro level ought to be moulded accordingly with entrepreneurial qualities and competencies to meet the adjustments in trends, challenges, and in addition to this to be in a position sufficient to sustain and attempt for excellence in the entrepreneurial arena. Every individual, family and the society has to contribute to the upliftment of business ideas and should encourage female entrepreneurs to chase their dreams with the right impetus to excel in their field.

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